

ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS FOR A NOVEL 3D-COMPOSITE PRODUCTION TECHNIQUE

Martin Eichenhofer¹, Jesus I. Maldonado¹, Florian Klunker¹, and Paolo Ermanni¹

¹Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Composite Materials and Adaptive Structures Lab,
ETH Zürich, Rämistrasse 101, 8092 Zurich, Switzerland
Emails: martin@eichenhofer.net, permanni@ethz.ch web page:
<http://www.structures.ethz.ch>

Keywords: 3D-Printing, Fiber Composite Extrusion, Free Form Structures, Lattice Structures, Thermoplastic Composites

ABSTRACT

In this work we propose a novel manufacturing process for a continuous fiber lattice fabrication (CFLF¹). The technology is inspired by conventional 3D-printing and represents a flexible manufacturing route without the use of additional bulky and expensive molds. The CFLF technology provides the ability to extrude free form structures of continuously reinforced polymeric material, thus showing the potential for fabricating fully integrated open-architecture composite lattice structures.

The novel two-stage extrusion head for the CFLF consists of two heating dies, along with necessary feeding and cooling attachments. The composite rods are produced using a commercially available thermoplastic commingled yarn material composed by carbon fibers and melt spun PA12 polymer fibers. Fiber impregnation and consolidation of the commingled yarns takes place in the first stage, while the second stage allows post-forming of the rod by active control and positioning of the extruder head.

The proposed CFLF extrusion technique is still in an early stage of development. This contribution is therefore focusing on straight composite rods and was aiming at identifying optimum processing conditions for the commingled yarns, considering three main process parameters, namely, line speed, die temperature, and outlet die diameter. A non-destructive method for estimating the void content is investigated. Based on this method, the rod roundness, dimensional repeatability and estimated void content were measured as a function of the processing conditions.

The concept is shown to be viable and has the potential to expand current capabilities in composite design by enabling the fabrication of free form composite architectures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The field of lightweight materials is one of the fastest growing market sectors in industry today [1]. In particular carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) show double digit growth potential within the next decade [2,3]. The potential for further innovation and commercialization of composite materials in lightweight design strongly depends on the availability of new manufacturing processes, enabling the fabrication of complex geometries, flexible fabrication routes and short cycle times.

Open-architecture lattice structures include amongst others pyramidal [4,5,6], Kangome [7,8,9], Cuboct [10] or anisogrid [11,12] structures. They have gained considerable attention in the last years. Compared to closed core architectures such as honeycombs[13], polymeric [14,15] and metal foams [16,17,18] or tangled materials [19,20], they exhibit exceptionally good specific mechanical properties [5,8,9,10]. Yet, manufacturability is a limiting factor for the commercialization of such promising architectures. Existing techniques involve multiple steps, require expensive and bulky molds and in many cases the application of adhesive joining techniques. As a matter of fact, commonly used manufacturing techniques such as filament winding [21,22], pultrusion [23,24,25], Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) [26,27], Automated Tape and Fiber Placement (ATP, AFP) [28,29] and injection molding [30,31], are not well suited for the fabrication of 3D open-cell architectures.

¹ Patented Technology

Thermoset matrices are not advantageous for the fabrication of latticed structures, because they require the utilization of rigid molds and do not provide significant forming capabilities after curing. We will therefore concentrate on thermoplastic matrix systems, because of their intrinsic formability. Furthermore, improved intermediate materials open-up for advanced fabrication technologies with free-forming capabilities, high flexibility and scalability such as robotic fiber placement of continuously reinforced polymers [32,33], thermoplastic stamp forming [34] and thermoplastic tape laying [35,36].

State of the art technologies for the rapid deposition of pre-impregnated thermoplastic tapes include automated tape laying (ATL) and automated fiber placement (AFP). Compaction rollers of different size ensure the required compaction pressure, which is applied against a rigid counter-mold. A form-giving reference geometry is also required by a promising technology recently presented by Markforged [37], which is a start-up company recently founded by Greg Mark in the USA. His team developed a 3D-printing technique for thermoplastic composite materials, which is working similarly to a conventional 3D printer by physically laying down layer upon layer. The remaining challenge consists thus in achieving forming and consolidating composite structures without the need of molds that dictate the composite's geometry.

In this work, 3D-printing is combined with a customized extrusion process, which enables a continuous fabrication of fiber lattice trusses. The so called Continuous Fiber Lattice Fabrication (CFLF) process is using a thermoplastic intermediate material consisting of commingled polyamide and carbon fibers. Commingled yarns [38,39] provide very good consolidation properties and seem therefore to be a good choice for this process technology.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic illustration of CFLF processing head, (b) CFLF prototyping machine.

A schematic illustration of the free form fabrication technique is depicted in Figure 1(a). The CFLF is a fully integrated manufacturing process, providing a flexible manufacturing route without the need for molds. As shown in Figure 1(b) a fiber composite rod is free-formed by an extrusion head that moves along a desired trajectory. The technique allows an integrated free forming of composite lattice structures onto a primary base substrate made of thermoplastic or thermoplastic fiber reinforced materials.

The objective of the presented research was to identify the influence of relevant processing parameters on the quality of the manufactured rods. The die swell effect has a large influence on the final quality of the rod. This phenomenon occurs due to reorientation of dislocated polymer molecules [40] and has been investigated for various material combinations [40,41,42,43,44]. While pultruding a unidirectional reinforced composite material, the die swell effect occurs, but is significantly reduced by

instant cooling and fiber straightening of the puller device [43]. Neither an analytic, nor an experimental investigation on the extrusion of continuous fiber reinforced polymers could be found in literature. Concerning the design of the processing head, the die outlet diameter is a critical parameter, which has to be tailored to the actual number of yarns fed, because a mismatch between those parameters is affecting the compaction of the intermediate material, thus causing an increased void content.

Preliminary investigations applying existing impregnation models for thermoplastic commingled yarns [45,46,47,48,49,50,51] indicated that following process parameters have a main influence on the laminate quality:

- (i) line speed of the extrusion,
- (ii) outlet die diameter,
- (iii) die temperature.

Straight rods were manufactured and analyzed with light microscopy to determine their morphology and their void content. Measurements of the rod-diameter were also carried out in order to evaluate the possibility to characterize the composite quality based on changes in the rod-diameter. Due to the good correlation with porosity measurements made using conventional light microscopy, we applied this characterization method to carry-out the comprehensive parametric study, eventually encompassing 1600 measurements.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1. Materials

The CFLF process is based on commingled yarns as intermediate material. Commingled yarns consist of thermoplastic matrix and reinforcement fibers commingled among each other, as illustrated in Figure 2, resulting in a reduced impregnation distance, while keeping the inherent flexibility of textiles. The yarn remains therefore easy to handle and feed, while keeping a very short impregnation time. Commercial fabrication processes include conjoining [39], air texturing [34] and stretch-broken spinning [38].

In this study we use continuous STS40 carbon fibers from Toho Tenax®, together with melt spun PA12 polymer fibers. The commingling process is done by Schappe Technologies [38] in France, which is commercializing the product under the name CDC 41815. Properties of the Toho Tenax® fiber and the PA12 polymer are summarized in Table 1.

Property	Abbreviation	Unit	Value
tensile strength fiber	σ_f	<i>MPa</i>	4000
tensile modulus fiber	E_f	<i>GPa</i>	240
max. elongation fiber	ε_f	%	1.73
density fiber	ρ_f	<i>kg/m³</i>	1770
tensile strength PA12	σ_m	<i>MPa</i>	55
tensile modulus PA12	E_m	<i>GPa</i>	1.27
max. elongation PA12	ε_m	%	33
density PA12	ρ_m	<i>kg/m³</i>	1010

Table 1: Properties STS40 fibers [52] and properties for PA12 [53]

Figure 2: Commingled yarn cross section

Three and seven yarns feed morphology are shown in Figure 3(a) and (b) respectively. These yarns consolidate into a single rod as shown in Figure 3(c) for the case of seven yarns. Given the yarn deformation as it occurs in reality for a pultrusion process, the original yarn feed morphology deviates, but it remains recognizable.

Figure 3: (a), (b) yarn feed morphology for hexagonal yarn packing, (c) microscopy cross-section of a fiber rod

2.2. Rod Quality Assessment

Void content of a fiber composite structure is the main parameter for evaluating the composite rod quality. Optical microscopy is a standard method to determine the void content. This procedure is quite time-consuming, involving cutting, grinding and polishing of the specimens, and also requiring special software tools for image processing.

In order to cope with the large amount of experiments planned within this parametric study, we developed a simplified quality characterization method, based on the measurement of the circumferential dimensions of the extruded rod. To this purpose, we assume that an ideal rod with 0% void content would perfectly match the cross-sectional area occupied by the fibers and the matrix only. Therefore an increase of the cross-sectional area of the rod can directly be correlated to the actual void content in the rod.

Given the preliminary character of the presented investigations, we think that this method is appropriate to provide an evaluation of the sensitivity of main processing parameters on the void content of the fabricated rod-elements. The parameters involved in the assessment of the rod quality are summarized in Table 2. The diameters of the rod were determined by a digital caliper. In order to further improve the accuracy of determining the measured rod diameter D_{mea} , four measurements were taken at 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° to form an averaged measured rod diameter \bar{D}_{mea} .

Variable	Expression	Description
A_v	—	Areal void content determined by light microscopy
A_N	—	Nominal cross sectional area
D_{mea}	—	Measured extruded rod diameter
D_{rod}	—	Nominal rod diameter at 0% void content
$\overline{A_v^{mea}}$	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{A_{v,i}}{A_N}$	Void content measured by light microscopy, as derived by an averaged sum of multiple measurements
$\overline{A_v^{cal}}$	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \left(\frac{\bar{D}_{mea,i}}{D_{rod}} \right) \right)$	Estimate of void content measured by caliper measurements, as derived by an averaged sum of multiple measurements
$\overline{roundness}$	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (\max\{D_{mea,ji}\} - \min\{D_{mea,ji}\})$	Determination of roundness, each cross section was measured at 4 different rod radial-angle positions 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° , represented by $i = 1,2,3,4$
$\overline{repeat\ accuracy}$	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\bar{D}_{MEA} - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{k=1}^4 D_{mea,jk} \right)^2$	Determination of variability of measured extruded rod diameters
$\overline{D_{MEA}}$	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{4} \sum_{k=1}^4 D_{mea,jk}$	Average rod thicknesses, measured by a caliper

Table 2: Definitions for the determination of fiber rod quality

2.3. Processing Conditions

The CFLF process includes a pultrusion and an extrusion stage. The focus of our investigation is lying on processing parameters related to the extrusion stage, because the composite quality is determined during this stage. The experimental program included therefore following parameters:

- V_{line} , line speed (extrusion speed)
- D_{out} , outlet die diameter
- T_{die} , die temperature

Whereof V_{line} and T_{die} are considered as processing parameters, and D_{out} as a die design parameter. A schematic cross section of the extrusion die is shown in Figure 4. This study investigates and quantifies the correlation between the processing conditions and its effect on the fiber rod quality.

Figure 4: Cross section extrusion die

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION FOR THE EXTRUSION OF CONTINUOUS FIBER COMPOSITE

3.1. Correlation of Image Analysis and Rod Diameters to Determine Void Content

As depicted in Figure 5, microscope void content measurements $\overline{A_v^{mea}}$ and caliper-based void content estimations $\overline{A_v^{cal}}$ are showing a good qualitative correlation. The presented correlation is based on the data of 15 optical microscopy analyses and 60 caliper measurements. Yet, the discrepancy between the two results amounts to approximately 4.1%. However, as the tendency is well described, the caliper based void content estimations provide a fast method for the characterization of rod quality.

Figure 5: Agreement between calculated ($\overline{A_v^{cal}}$) and measured void content ($\overline{A_v^{mea}}$)

3.2. Effect of Outlet Die Diameter and Line Speed on Void Content

The relationship between outlet die diameter (D_{out}), line speed (V_{line}) and resulting void content is presented in Figure 6. The extrusion die temperature was kept constant at $T_{die} = 230^\circ C$. A total of 192 rod measurements were taken for deriving this diagram.

Figure 6: Influence of outlet die diameter D_{out} and line speed V_{line} on estimated void content

Overall the void content is still quite high. The results show a clear tendency of increased void content towards higher line speeds, which can be associated to polymer molecule reorientation (mostly in the periphery), causing the extrudate to swell. In this context, swelling is defined as the radial enlargement of the extrudate after leaving the extrusion die. Another factor possibly playing a role in extrudate swelling is fiber compaction. The fiber tows are squeezed together within the die, so fiber waviness and misalignment cause a spring-like characteristic. The unloading of the spring after leaving the die, which is facilitated by the not yet solidified polymer, can be a cause of swelling (i.e. voids). A slower speed results in an increased residence time of the commingled fibers inside the extrusion die. The extended time inside the die would allow the fibers to rearrange themselves, reducing the spring-back force. Moreover, the increased time inside the die would transfer more thermal energy and further reduce the viscosity of the polymer, thus further increasing fiber mobilization and rearrangement. A fast line speed might provide too little time for the reinforcement fibers to correct their misalignment during matrix flow/consolidation, which together with hindered fiber mobility due to higher viscosity, result in high stored spring-back forces.

The hypothesis of the fiber compaction role in swelling is coherent with the observations for the enlarged outlet die diameter D_{out} . The nominal outlet die diameter is $D_{out} = 1.43\text{mm}$. A slightly enlarged diameter, in this case by 10%, hardly affects the void content due to reduced compaction pressure, preventing radial rod enlargement. However, further enlargement of the extrusion die diameter has a strong negative impact on the void content due to the lack of compaction pressure. The quality change of the extruded rods with increasing line speed seems to be insensitive to slightly enlarged extrusion die diameters, as all the curves have a similar slope.

3.3. Effect of Extrusion Die Temperature and Line Speed on Void Content

In the following we conducted a comprehensive experimental study to determine the influence of the extrusion die temperature on the composite quality. In addition to the determination of the void content $\overline{A_v^{cal}}$ we also evaluated the roundness (*roundness*) of the specimens and repeatability (*repeat accuracy*) of the process. The study was conducted with the nominal outlet die diameter of $D_{out} = 1.43\text{mm}$. Both, the processing line speed V_{line} and the processing temperature T_{die} were varied. The goal was to determine advantageous temperature domains for the individual extrusion velocities. A total of 1440 rod measurements were carried-out. Results are shown Figure 7.

The optimal temperature regions differ according to quality criteria and line speed. Hence, to determine an ideal temperature setting, a compromise between the three quality criteria has to be made. The best compromise temperature regions are circled red in Figure 7, which shift from slow line speeds at high die temperature to high line speeds and low die temperature.

The shift of the optimal zones can be explained by the interacting factors. It seems that a slow line speed, which possesses a longer cooling time at the outlet of the extrusion orifice, can benefit from higher die temperatures that reduce retraction forces of the polymeric material. These reduced retractions force then cause a reduced swelling effect during the extended time when they act, improving rod quality. In contrast, a fast line speed has less cooling time at the outlet, and hence, can benefit from an initial high viscosity at a reduced die temperature.

Figure 7: Correlation between quality criteria and die temperature/line speed

The diagram in Figure 7 also reveals the process boundaries. The tendency in the optimal zones is disrupted by line speeds exceeding 200mm/min where not all polymeric fibers of the commingled yarn material were molten. If the heat flow at high speeds is not sufficient anymore to completely liquefy the matrix material, it will mark a clear top-speed boundary for the processing conditions of this investigation using the current setup. This knowledge is used to determine an ideal processing window for the CFLF extrusion process of continuous fiber composite material with the current setup (Figure 8).

The shaded region is constrained by four boundaries. A limiting factor for the upper bound is the tendency of the repeat accuracy. The lower bound is dictated by a compromise between all quality factors. An insufficient heat flow applies for the right bound at speeds exceeding 200mm/min. No left bound is depicted in the diagram, continuing until the degradation of matrix material starts. The red dot in the diagram indicates the processing point selected for further CFLF processing investigations.

Figure 8: Ideal processing domain for the CFLF technique

4 CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a novel mold-free technique for the fabrication of unidirectional composite lattice structures and investigated the relationship between processing conditions in terms of line speed, die temperature, outlet die diameter and quality of the fabricated components. Among the different parameters, the die swell effect seems to have the most relevant influence on the final part quality. Our investigations further demonstrated the flexibility of the process in terms of achievable line speed and controller temperature, thus confirming the proof of concept for the free-form printing of 3D composite latticed structures.

For the characterization of the void content we adopted a novel method, which is relying on simple geometrical considerations. This method shows a good qualitative correlation with conventional methods on optical microscopy.

The proposed CFLF extrusion technique is still in an early stage of development, but can be considered the first fully integrated manufacturing technique for 3D composite lattice structures. It bears high potential to open-up new fabrication routes for free form composite architectures, e.g. lattice structures. The flexible fabrication route is enhancing design-freedom, enabling the realization of new, and even more efficient lightweight architectures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We acknowledge Schappe Technologies for providing the precursor material, the chair of Product Development at ETH Zurich for supporting the work with a 3D-printer, and Florian Eichenhofer for the support received throughout the development of the CFLF composite production technique.

REFERENCES

- [1] McKinsey&Company Germany, <http://www.mckinsey.de/co2-regulierung-sorgt-bis-2030-f%C3%BCr-dreistelliges-milliardenwachstum-im-leichtbau>
- [2] Roland Berger Strategy Consultants, Demand For High-Strength Carbon-Fiber Composite Components Rising By 17% A Year, Frankfurt/Munich, September 26, 2012 (http://www.rolandberger.com/press_releases/512-press_archive2012_sc_content/High_strength_carbon_fiber_composite_components.html).

- [3] M. Holmes, *Carbon fibre reinforced plastics market continues growth path*, Reinforced Plastics, November/December 2013. (<http://www.reinforcedplastics.com/view/36341/carbon-fibre-reinforced-plastics-market-continues-growth-path-part-1/>) ***
- [4] B. Wang, L. Wu, L. Ma, Y. Sun and S. Du, Mechanical behavior of the sandwich structures with carbon reinforced pyramidal lattice truss core. *Materials & Design*, **31-5**, 2010, pp. 2659–2663 (doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2009.11.061).
- [5] G. Zhang, B. Wang, L. Ma, J. Xiong, J. Yang and L. Wu, The residual compressive strength of impact-damaged sandwich structures with pyramidal truss cores. *Composite Structures*, **105**, 2013, pp. 188-198 (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.05.016).
- [6] G. W. Kooistra, V. S. Deshpande and H. N.G Wadley, Compressive behavior of age hardenable tetrahedral lattice truss structures made from aluminium. *Acta Materialia*, **52-14**, 2004, pp. 4229-4237 (doi:10.1016/j.actamat.2004.05.039).
- [7] B. Lee, K. Lee, J. Byun and K. Kang, The compressive response of new composite truss cores, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **43-2**, 2012, pp. 317-324 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.08.048).
- [8] M. Lee and K. Kang, Feasibility of a wire-woven metal for application as a sandwich core, *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, **80**, 2014, pp. 81-92 (doi:10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2014.01.004).
- [9] M.G. Lee, J.W. Yoon, S.M. Han, Y.S. Suh and K.J. Kang, In-plane compression response of wirewoven metal cored sandwich panels. *Materials & Design*, **55**, 2014, pp. 718–726 (doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2013.08.066).
- [10] K.C Cheung and N. Gershenfeld. Reversibly assembled cellular composite materials. *Science*, **341-6151**, pp. 1219-1221 (doi: 10.1126/science.1240889)
- [11] V.V. Vasiliev, V.A. Barynin and A.F. Razin, Anisogrid composite lattice structures – development and aerospace applications. *Composite Structures*, **94-3**, 2012, pp. 1117–1127 (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.10.023)
- [12] H. Fan, L. Yanga, F. Sun and Daining Fang, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **52**, 2013, pp. 118–125 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2013.04.013)
- [13] Q. Chen, N. Pugno, K. Zhao and Z. Li. Mechanical properties of a hollow-cylindrical-joint honeycomb. *Composite Structures*, *Composite Structures*, **109**, 2014, pp. 68–74 (doi: 10.1016/j.compstruct.2013.10.025)
- [14] Z. Y. Awad, T. Aravinthan and Y. Zhuge, Experimental and numerical analysis of an innovative gfrp sandwich core panel under point load. *Engineering Structures*, **41**, 2012, pp. 126–135. (doi: 10.1016/j.engstruct.2012.03.023)
- [15] A. Fam and T. Sharaf, Flexural performance of sandwich panels comprising polyurethane core and GFRP skins and ribs of various configurations. *Composite Structures*, **92-12**, 2010, pp. 2927–2935. (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2010.05.004).
- [16] J.K. Khabushan, S.B. Bonabi, F.M. Aghbagh and A.K.Khabushan, A study of fabricating and compressive properties of cellular Al-Si (355.0) foam using TiH₂. *Materials & Design*, **55**, 2014, pp. 792–797 (doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2013.10.022)
- [17] P. Pinto, N. Peixinho, F. Silva and D. Soares, Compressive properties and energy absorption of aluminum foams with modified cellular geometry. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **214-3**, 2014, pp. 571–577 (doi:10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2013.11.011).
- [18] D.P. Kou, J.R. Li, J.L. Yu and H.F. Cheng, Mechanical behavior of open cell metallic foams with dual-size cellular structure. *Scripta Materialia*, **59-5**, 2008, pp. 483–486 (doi:10.1016/j.scriptamat.2008.04.022).
- [19] D. Zhang, F. Scarpa, Y. Ma, K. Boba, J. Hong and H. Lu, Compression mechanics of nickel-based superalloy metal rubber. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, **580**, 2013, pp. 305–312 (doi:10.1016/j.msea.2013.05.064).
- [20] D. Zhang, F. Scarpa, Y. Ma, J. Hong and Y. Mahadik, Dynamic mechanical behavior of nickelbased superalloy metal rubber. *Materials & Design*, **56**, 2014, pp. 69–77 (doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2013.10.088). ***

- [21] R. Gennaro, F. Montagna, A. Maffezzoli, F. Fracasso and S. Fracasso, On-line consolidation of commingled polypropylene/glass roving during filament winding. *Journal of composite materials*, **24-6**, 2011, pp. 789-804 (doi: 10.1177/0892705711401849)
- [22] S.D. Pandita, M.S. Irfan, V.R. Machavaram, N. Shotton-Gale, R.S. Mahendran, C.F. Wait, M.A. Paget, D. Harris, C. Leek and G.F. Fernando, Clean wet-filament winding – Part 1: design concept and simulations, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **47-3**, 2013, pp. 379-390 (doi:10.1177/0021998312440474).
- [23] G. R. Stroehrer, E. L. Zapparoli and C. R. de Andrade, Parabolic modeling of the pultrusion process with thermal property variation. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, **42**, 2013, pp. 32–37 (doi:10.1016/j.icheatmasstransfer.2012.12.010).
- [24] J. B. Nunes, J. F. Silva and P. J. Novo, Processing thermoplastic matrix towpregs by pultrusion, *Advances in Polymer Technology*, **32-S1**, 2013, pp. E306–E312 (DOI: 10.1002/adv.21279)
- [25] S. Koubaa, S. Le Corre and C. Burtin, Thermoplastic pultrusion process: Modeling and optimal conditions for fibers impregnation. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, **32-17**, 2013, pp. 1285-1294 (doi: 10.1177/0731684413489851)
- [26] T. Brocks, M. Shiino, M. Cioffi, H. Voorwald and A. Filho. Experimental RTM manufacturing analysis of carbon/epoxy composites for aerospace application: non-crimp and woven fabric differences, *Mat. Res.*, **16**, 2013 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S1516-14392013005000107>)
- [27] B. Louis, J.I. Maldonado, F. Klunker and P. Ermanni, "Measurement of Nanoparticle Distribution in Composite Laminates Produced by Resin Transfer Molding" *ECCM16, Seville, Spain, June 22nd-26th, 2014*
- [28] D. Lukaszewicz, C. Ward and K. P. Potter. The engineering aspect of automated prepreg layup: History, present and future. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **43-3**, 2012, pp. 997–1009 (doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.12.003)
- [29] P. Debout, H. Chanal and E. Duc, Tool path smoothing of a redundant machine: Application to automated fiber placement. *Computer-Aided Design*, **43-2**, 2011, pp. 122–132 (doi:10.1016/j.cad.2010.09.011)
- [30] E. W. Liang and V. K. Stokes, Mechanical properties of injection-molded short-fiber thermoplastic composites. Part 1: The elastic moduli and strengths of glass-filled poly (butylene terephthalate), *Polymer composites*, **26-4**, 2005, pp. 428-447 (DOI: 10.1002/pc.20073)
- [31] Patcharaphun, Somjate, and G. Mennig. "Properties enhancement of short glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastics via sandwich injection molding." *Polymer composites*, **26-6**, 2005, pp. 823-831 (DOI: 10.1002/pc.20149)
- [32] M.D. Wakeman, P.-E. Bourban, F. Bonjour, P. Berguerand, J.-A. E. Månson, A novel manufacturing cell for a new generation of composite processing and applications. *Proceedings of ICCM-12, Paris (1999)*.
- [33] M. D. Wakeman, P.-O. Hagstrand, F. Bonjour, P.-E. Bourban, and J.-A. E. Månson. Robotic tow placement for local reinforcement of glass mat thermoplastics (GMTs), *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **33-9**, 2002, pp. 1199-1208. (doi:10.1016/S1359-835X(02)00086-6)
- [34] U. Thomann, M. Sauter and P. Ermanni, A combined impregnation and heat transfer model for stamp forming of unconsolidated commingled yarn preforms. *Composites Science and Technology*, **64**, 2004, pp. 1637-1651. (doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2003.12.002)
- [35] A. Beakou, M. Cano, J.-B. Le Cam, and V. Verney. "Modelling slit tape buckling during automated prepreg manufacturing: A local approach." *Composite Structures*, **93-10**, 2011, pp. 2628-2635. (doi:10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.04.030)
- [36] H. Dirk, H.-J.A. Lukaszewicz, C. Ward, and K. D. Potter. "The engineering aspects of automated prepreg layup: History, present and future." *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **43-3**, 2012, pp. 997-1009. (doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2011.12.003)
- [37] MarkForged, Greg Mark, The World's first carbon fiber 3D-printer. (<https://markforged.com>)
- [38] Schappe Technologies. Commingled carbon fiber yarns. 01150 Blyes, France. (<http://www.schappe.com/en/rd>)

- [39] N. Bernet, V. Michaud, P.-E. Bourban and J.-A.E. Månson, Commingled yarn composites for rapid processing of complex shapes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **32-11**, 2001, pp. 1613–1626 (doi:10.1016/S1359-835X(00)00180-9).
- [40] K. C. M. Nair, R. P. Kumar, S. Thomas, S. C. Schit, and K. Ramamurthy, Rheological behavior of short sisal fiber-reinforced polystyrene composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **31-11**, 2000, pp. 1231-1240. (doi:10.1016/S1359-835X(00)00083-X)
- [41] G. Kalaprasad, G. Mathew, C. Pavithran, and Sabu Thomas, Melt rheological behavior of intimately mixed short sisal–glass hybrid fiber-reinforced low-density polyethylene composites. I. Untreated fibers, *Journal of applied polymer science*, **89-2**, 2003, pp. 432-442. (DOI: 10.1002/app.11975)
- [42] Chiu, Wen-Yen, and Goang-Ding Shyu, The study on die swell, fiber length distribution, and crystallinity of PP composite through extrusion, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **34-4**, 1987, pp. 1493-1501. (DOI: 10.1002/app.1987.070340413)
- [43] S. Middleman, J. Greener, and M. Malone. *Fundamentals of polymer processing*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1977.
- [44] F. Hensen, *Plastics extrusion technology*, C. Hanser Verlag, Munich, 1988
- [45] Bernet, N., V. Michaud, P. E. Bourban, and J. A. E. Manson. "An impregnation model for the consolidation of thermoplastic composites made from commingled yarns." *Journal of composite materials*, **33-8**, 1999, pp. 751-772. (doi: 10.1177/002199839903300806)
- [46] L. Ye, K. Friedrich, J. Kästel, and Y. Mai, Consolidation of unidirectional CF/PEEK composites from commingled yarn prepreg, *Composites science and technology*, **54-4**, 1995, pp. 349-358. (doi:10.1016/0266-3538(95)00061-5)
- [47] K. C. M. Nair, R. P. Kumar, S. Thomas, S. C. Schit, and K. Ramamurthy, Rheological behavior of short sisal fiber-reinforced polystyrene composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **31-11**, 2000, pp. 1231-1240 (doi:10.1016/S1359-835X(00)00083-X)
- [48] D.-H. Kim, W. Lee, K. Friedrich, A model for thermoplastic pultrusion process using commingled yarns *Composites Science and Technology*, **61-8**, 2001, pp. 1065-1077 (doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(00)00234-7)
- [49] D.-H.Kim, P.-G. Han, F.-H. Jin and W.I. Lee, A model for thermosetting composite pultrusion process. *Journal of Composite Materials*, **31-20**, 1997, pp. 2105-2122. (doi: 10.1177/002199839703102005)
- [50] K Van de Velde, P Kiekens. Thermoplastic pultrusion of natural fibre reinforced composites, *Composite Structure*, **54-2**, 2001, pp. 355-360. (doi:10.1016/S0263-8223(01)00110-6)
- [51] B. P. Van West, R. Byron Pipes, and S. G. Advani, The consolidation of commingled thermoplastic fabrics, *Polymer composites*, **12-6**, 1991, pp. 417-427. (DOI: 10.1002/pc.750120607)
- [52] Toho Tenax. STS40 carbon fiber. (<http://www.tohotenax-eu.com/>)
- [53] EFUNDA. Properties PA12 (nylon). (http://www.efunda.com/materials/polymers/properties/polymer_datasheet.cfm?MajorID=PA&MinorID=81)